

A NONLINEAR VISCOELASTIC CONSTITUTIVE MODEL FOR RAYON CORD REINFORCED RUBBER

Xingwen Du, Hao Ma, Qihua Zhang
Harbin Institute of Technology

ABSTRACT

Rayon cord reinforced rubber(RCRR) is a sort of flexible composites, which is widely used as structure materials of tires and other rubber products. Its mechanical behavior presents marked viscoelastic characteristics. Based on Green-Rivlin theory and the assumption about linear-viscosity and nonlinear-elasticity a nonlinear viscoelastic constitutive model for RCRR is suggested in this paper. The experimental results confirm that this constitutive model may describe the behavior of RCRR under conditions of stress-relaxation and creep along material principal axes of RCRR well.

Keywords: reinforced rubber, viscoelasticity, constitutive model

1. INTRODUCTION

Polymer cord reinforced elastomer(PCRE) forms a special sort of composite materials, it is called as flexible composite. Usually the mechanical behavior of RCRR is effected by time, temperature and strain rate. It is a viscoelastic material. Rayon cord reinforced rubber (RCRR) is a kind of PCRE. It is widely used in the rubber industry. A nonlinear viscoelastic constitutive model for RCRR is suggested in this paper. It is supposed that the nonlinearity is only concerned with elasticity of the material, and is not related to viscosity. It is called as assumption about nonlinear-elasticity and linear-viscosity. When applying this assumption to Green-Rivlin theory, the constitutive equation for RCRR is achieved. A large number of experimental results confirm that this constitutive model may describe the behavior of RCRR under the conditions of stress-relaxation and creep along material principal axes of RCRR well.

2. CONSTITUTIVE MODEL

2.1. Green-Rivlin Theory

The description of motion of a particle in a body of material may be denoted by

$$x_i = x_i(X_j, \tau) \quad (i, j = 1, 2, 3) \quad (0 \leq \tau \leq t) \quad (1)$$

Where X_j and x_i are coordinates of the material particle relative to an initial state and the state at time τ respectively. It is supposed that stress in the material depends only on the history of the deformation gradients F_{rs} . Thus material is called as a simple material[1,2]. The constitutive relation of the material may be expressed as

$$\sigma(t) = \mathcal{F}_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \{F(\tau)\} \quad (2)$$

Where \mathcal{F} is a functional, σ is a stress tensor. After several operations, see[1], expression(2) may become as

$$\Sigma(t) = \mathcal{H}'_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \{E(\tau)\} \quad (3)$$

Where \mathcal{H} is an isotropic functional, Σ is a stress matrix expressed by

$$\Sigma(t) = R^T \sigma(t) R \quad (4)$$

Where R is a rotation matrix, it is an orthogonol, E is a strain measure tensor, which is defined by

$$E_{ij} = \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial X_j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial X_i} + \frac{\partial u_k}{\partial X_i} \frac{\partial u_k}{\partial X_j} \quad (5)$$

Where u is a displacement vector.

The polynomial integral expression for \mathcal{H} has been given by Green and Rivlin[1] as following

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma(t) = & \int_{-\infty}^t \{I\zeta_1(\text{tr}\dot{E}(\tau_1)) + \zeta_2\dot{E}(\tau_1)\} d\tau_1 + \int \int_{-\infty}^t \{I\zeta_3(\text{tr}\dot{E}(\tau_1))(\text{tr}\dot{E}(\tau_2)) \\ & + I\zeta_4(\text{tr}\dot{E}(\tau_1)\dot{E}(\tau_2)) + \zeta_5(\text{tr}\dot{E}(\tau_1))\dot{E}(\tau_2) + \zeta_6\dot{E}(\tau_1)\dot{E}(\tau_2)\} d\tau_1 d\tau_2 \\ & + \int \int \int_{-\infty}^t \{I\zeta_7(\text{tr}\dot{E}(\tau_1)\dot{E}(\tau_2)\dot{E}(\tau_3)) + I\zeta_8(\text{tr}\dot{E}(\tau_1))(\text{tr}\dot{E}(\tau_2)\dot{E}(\tau_3)) \\ & + \zeta_9(\text{tr}\dot{E}(\tau_1))(\text{tr}\dot{E}(\tau_2))\dot{E}(\tau_3) + \zeta_{10}(\text{tr}\dot{E}(\tau_1)\dot{E}(\tau_2))\dot{E}(\tau_3) \\ & + \zeta_{11}(\text{tr}\dot{E}(\tau_1))\dot{E}(\tau_2)\dot{E}(\tau_3) + \zeta_{12}\dot{E}(\tau_1)\dot{E}(\tau_2)\dot{E}(\tau_3)\} d\tau_1 d\tau_2 d\tau_3 + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Where ζ_α are stress-relaxation functions of various orders. The nth order function ζ_n is a function of n variables.

For one dimensional case the constitutive relation(6) becomes the following form

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma(t) = & \int_{-\infty}^t \Phi_1(t-\tau_1) \dot{E}(\tau_1) d\tau_1 + \int \int_{-\infty}^t \Phi_2(t-\tau_1, t-\tau_2) \dot{E}(\tau_1) \dot{E}(\tau_2) d\tau_1 d\tau_2 \\ & + \int \int \int_{-\infty}^t \Phi_3(t-\tau_1, t-\tau_2, t-\tau_3) \dot{E}(\tau_1) \dot{E}(\tau_2) \dot{E}(\tau_3) d\tau_1 d\tau_2 d\tau_3 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

If rotation of material elements is small, $\mathbf{R} \approx \mathbf{I}$, the expression(7) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma(t) = & \int_{-\infty}^t \Phi_1(t-\tau_1) \dot{E}(\tau_1) d\tau_1 + \int \int_{-\infty}^t \Phi_2(t-\tau_1, t-\tau_2) \dot{E}(\tau_1) \dot{E}(\tau_2) d\tau_1 d\tau_2 \\ & + \int \int \int_{-\infty}^t \Phi_3(t-\tau_1, t-\tau_2, t-\tau_3) \dot{E}(\tau_1) \dot{E}(\tau_2) \dot{E}(\tau_3) d\tau_1 d\tau_2 d\tau_3 \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

It is the stress-relaxation form of the constitutive relation of Green-Rivlin theory for one-dimensional case. The creep form corresponding to the expression(8) is readily shown as

$$\begin{aligned} E(t) = & \int_{-\infty}^t \Psi_1(t-\tau_1) \sigma(\tau_1) d\tau_1 + \int \int_{-\infty}^t \Psi_2(t-\tau_1, t-\tau_2) \sigma(\tau_1) \sigma(\tau_2) d\tau_1 d\tau_2 \\ & + \int \int \int_{-\infty}^t \Psi_3(t-\tau_1, t-\tau_2, t-\tau_3) \sigma(\tau_1) \sigma(\tau_2) \sigma(\tau_3) d\tau_1 d\tau_2 d\tau_3 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

2.2. Assumption for RCRR

It is supposed that the nonlinearity of the constitutive characteristics of RCRR is only concerned with elasticity, is not a much related to viscosity. It is called as assumption about nonlinear-elasticity and linear-viscosity for RCRR.

2.3. The Constitutive Equation for RCRR

According to above constitutive model, the material functions in Green-Rivlin relation(8) can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_1 = & A_{10} + A_{11} \exp\left(-\frac{t-\tau}{\vartheta_1}\right) + A_{12} \exp\left(-\frac{t-\tau}{\vartheta_2}\right) + \dots + A_{1m} \exp\left(-\frac{t-\tau}{\vartheta_m}\right) + \dots \\ \Phi_2 = & A_{20} \\ \Phi_3 = & A_{30} \\ & \vdots \\ \Phi_n = & A_{n0} \end{aligned}$$

The viscous terms only appear in the linear function Φ_1 . Only first three functions and first three terms in function Φ_1 are retained for RCRR so that

$$\begin{aligned}\Phi_1 &= A_{10} + A_{11} \exp\left(-\frac{t-\tau}{\vartheta_1}\right) + A_{12} \exp\left(-\frac{t-\tau}{\vartheta_2}\right) \\ \Phi_2 &= A_{20} \\ \Phi_3 &= A_{30}\end{aligned}\quad (11)$$

Finally, the nonlinear viscoelastic constitutive equation for RCRR is obtained by substituting from (11) into (8)

$$\sigma(t) = A_{10}E + A_{20}E^2 + A_{30}E^3 + \int_{-\infty}^t [A_{11} \exp\left(-\frac{t-\tau}{\vartheta_1}\right) + A_{12} \exp\left(-\frac{t-\tau}{\vartheta_2}\right)] E d\tau \quad (12)$$

where A_{mn} are the material constants, ϑ_i are also material constants called as relaxation times. It is in the stress-relaxation form of one dimension. The creep form corresponding to (11) and (12) can be readily achieved.

$$\begin{aligned}\Psi_1 &= B_{10} - B_{11} \exp\left(-\frac{t-\tau}{\chi_1}\right) - B_{12} \exp\left(-\frac{t-\tau}{\chi_2}\right) \\ \Psi_2 &= B_{20} \\ \Psi_3 &= B_{30}\end{aligned}\quad (13)$$

$$E(t) = B_{10}\sigma + B_{20}\sigma^2 + B_{30}\sigma^3 - \int_{-\infty}^t [B_{11} \exp\left(-\frac{t-\tau}{\chi_1}\right) + B_{12} \exp\left(-\frac{t-\tau}{\chi_2}\right)] \sigma d\tau \quad (14)$$

3. EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

3.1. Experimental Conditions

A lot of tests on stress-relaxation and creep for RCRR had been completed to verify above constitutive model. All tests were conducted by using INSTRON 1186 testing machine.

The specimens used in this study are made of unidirectional RCRR. The specimen dimensions are 400×25×3 mm. The speed of initial deformation is 100 mm/min. The maximum deformation does not exceed 10%. The experimental temperature is about 24 °C.

3.2. Stress-Relaxation Tests

For single step experiments of stress-relaxation, the material specimen is now subjected at time $t=0$ to a suddenly applied strain which is maintained constant thereafter[3]. Thus applied strain has the form

$$E(t) - E_0 H(t) \quad (15)$$

Where E_0 is a constant, $H(t)$ denotes the Heaviside step function, $H(t)=0, t < 0; H(t)=1, t \geq 0$. Substituting (15) into (12) yields

$$\sigma(t) - (A_{10} - A_{11} \hat{\nu}_1 - A_{12} \hat{\nu}_2) E_0 + A_{20} E_0^2 + A_{30} E_0^3 + A_{11} E_0 \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\hat{\nu}_1}\right) + A_{12} E_0 \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\hat{\nu}_2}\right) \quad (16)$$

The theoretical curves of longitudinal and transverse stress-relaxation for RCRR are compared with experimental results as shown in Fig.1 and Fig.2, respectively. From these curves it can be seen that the theoretical curves conform to the experimental results well.

3.3. Creep Tests

For single step experiments of creep the material specimens now subjected at time $t=0$ to a suddenly applied stress which is maintained constant thereafter[3]. Thus applied stress has the form

$$\sigma(t) - \sigma_0 H(t) \quad (17)$$

Where σ_0 is a constant. Substituting (17) into (14) yields

$$E(t) - (B_{10} + B_{11} \chi_1 + B_{12} \chi_2) \sigma_0 + B_{20} \sigma_0^2 + B_{30} \sigma_0^3 - B_{11} \sigma_0 \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\chi_1}\right) - B_{12} \sigma_0 \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\chi_2}\right) \quad (18)$$

The theoretical curves of longitudinal and transverse creep for RCRR are compared with experimental results as shown in Fig.3 and Fig.4 respectively. They indicate that the theoretical predictions conform with experimental results well. However the conformability between theoretical and experimental for longitudinal creep is a little better than that for transverse.

4. SUMMARY

The nonlinear viscoelastic constitutive model for RCRR is suggested based on the assumption about nonlinear-elasticity and linear-viscosity. While the model is applied to Green_Rivlin theory the constitutive equation for RCRR is achieved.

Experiments confirm that this constitutive equation is used for describing the behavior of RCRR under stress-relaxation and creep along its material principal axes well.

Whether this constitutive model is applicable for other deformation conditions of RCRR it remains to be proved by further works.

Acknowledgements--This project was supported by the National Natural Science Foundation

of China.

References

1. Lockett, F. J., Nonlinear Viscoelastic Solids, Academic Press Inc., New York 1972, pp. 59-95
2. Christensen, R.M., Theory of Viscoelasticity, An Introduction, Second Edition, Academic Press Inc., New York 1982, pp. 271
3. Ferry, J. D., Viscoelastic Properties of Polymers, Third Edition, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., New York 1980, pp.154-168

Figure 1 Theoretical Curves for Longitudinal Stress-relaxation of RCRR Compared with Experimental Results

Figure 2 Theoretical Curves for Transverse Stress-relaxation of RCRR Compared with Experimental Results

Figure 3 Theoretical Curves for Longitudinal Creep of RCRR Are Compared with Experimental Results

Figure 4 Theoretical Curves for Transverse Creep of RCRR Are Compared with Experimental Results